

GENERATION IDEAL TEST IMAGES

D.G. Otkupman

Moscow State University of Geodesy and Cartography (MIIGAiK)

odvk@ya.ru

We consider the software implementation of the forming of a set of test images by the strictly described mathematical functions. These images can serve as reference patterns when studying the quality of the output image of an optoelectronic system model and analyzing the disturbances introduced by it. Such patterns can also be used in testing methods of digital image processing or computer (machine) vision, in analyzing the quality of digital printing, in creating targets and in other applications.

Binary examples of generated test images based on simple geometric primitives, raster fields of point, linear and radial-sector type, checkerboard, "chirped", circular, spiral, sinusoidal, star-shaped and other structures are presented in the figure.

Figure. Examples of test images